

POTENTIAL GROSS ECONOMIC IMPACTS OF CREATIVE INFORMATICS PROGRAMME 2019/20 TO 2025/26

ASSESSMENT BY DR MARK GRAHAM, LEAD
ECONOMIST, DATA DRIVEN INNOVATION
PROGRAMME, UNIVERSITY OF EDINBURGH

June 2024

This report is published under open license (CC-BY).

Please cite as:

Graham, M. (2024) Potential Gross Economic Impacts of Creative Informatics Programme 2029/20 to 2025/26 (Version 1). Zenodo. <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.12206071>

CREATIVE INFORMATICS: UPDATED IMPACT ANALYSIS

INTRODUCTION

In September 2023 an initial assessment – as attached at Appendix A – was made of the potential current and future gross economic impacts of the Creative Informatics (CI) programme. The data upon which this analysis was based has now been updated. Outlined below are the consequent impacts of including this data together with the key assumptions upon which these updates are based.

Based on current CI estimates of job levels generated or safeguarded by the programme over 2019/20 to 2022/23, and accounting for subsequent programme participants business inactivity rates, Table One indicates a total (gross) level of £33.1 million Gross Value Added to the Scottish economy may be associated with the CI Programme.

TABLE ONE: ESTIMATES OF DIRECT CURRENT CI GROSS GVA LEVELS 2019/20 TO 2022/23

	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	Total
Total New or Safeguarded Jobs (including 10 CI Team Members)	71.5	152.5	252	405	
“Average” GVA per head in current price terms	33,300	33,850	37,000	40,000	
Total	£2.4m	£5.2m	£9.3m	£16.2m	£33.1m

As indicated, in Table Two below, if the 2022/23 participant job levels were to be maintained (i.e. assuming an even balance between some participant’s organisations experiencing job growth while others may become inactive) then over the next three years a further £45.5 million GVA (in current price terms) might be generated.

TABLE TWO: POTENTIAL FUTURE GROSS IMPACTS IN CURRENT PRICE TERMS 2023/4 TO 2026/26

	2023/4	2024/5	2025/6	
Total Jobs ¹	395	395	395	
“Average” net present value ² GVA per head	£40,000	£38,648	£36,077	
Total	£15.8m	£15.3m	£14.3m	£45.4m

Combining the two estimates above suggests a gross total of £78.5 million GVA might be associated with the programme by 2025/26.

KEY ASSUMPTIONS

The analysis above is based on a series of assumptions, namely:

- The majority of impacts can be captured from the estimates of the total 395 jobs safeguarded or created (by 2022/3) as a result of participation in four of the CI programme activities (i.e. as illustrated in Table A1 Annex A: Challenge, Connected, Residential Entrepreneurs and Creative Bridge);
- Excluded from the current analysis, again as illustrated by Table A1, are any impacts associated with the 187 Minimum Viable Product (MVP) Activities under Creative Bridge; 3 Creative Horizon and 6 Lab products, services and experiences; and, the 339 training participants under Studios. While these elements may generate further impacts they have currently been excluded because:
 - No evidence was provided of MVP outcomes (which over time if successfully commercialised could have significant relative impacts);
 - No jobs either safeguarded or created were recorded under the Creative Horizon or Lab projects; and,
 - Given the nature of training provided (i.e. in most cases CPDs) to the 339 participants (under Studios) it is unlikely that this support will have a material impact.³
- Estimates of the GVA per employee are drawn from Scottish Annual Business Statistics data sets. Given the diverse nature of CI participants an average value has been adopted across three sectors, namely: the average GVA per employee in the Scottish Arts

¹ Excluding CI Team members.

² “The Green Book recommends that costs and benefits occurring in the first 30 years of a programme, project or policy be discounted at an annual rate of 3.5%”. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/green-book-supplementary-guidance-discounting>

³ i.e. under the economic cases for all DDI hubs the benefit ascribed to CPDs was 3.6 x the individual cost of a paid for course. Assuming, therefore, that the opportunity cost of a CI CPD was £500 the 339 participants could be ascribed a one-off annual uplift of £170,000.

Entertainment and Recreation sector (over 2018 to 2020); Scottish Creative Industries (excluding the public sector) over 2019 to 2021; and, Sustainable Tourism Sector over 2019 to 2021.

ANNEX A

Table A1 outlines CI activities (i.e. in the first column under “programmes”), the KPIs recorded for each of these activities (i.e. jobs, MVPs etc.) the assumptions drawn for each programme in estimating gross impacts and the consequent coverage of the analysis (in green shaded cells) as well as the “gaps” (in the yellow shaded cells) that are implied by these assumptions

TABLE A1: CI ACTIVITIES AND KPIs

Programme	Jobs (Safe Guarded or New)	Spin outs, start-ups and pivots	MVPs	Products, Services, Experiences	Training	Assumptions
Challenge	52	5	12	31		Job impacts fully capture benefits of the Challenge Programme
Connected Innovator	57		4	50	27	Job impacts fully capture benefits of the Connected Programme
Resident Entrepreneurs	216	17	34	86	74	Job impacts fully capture benefits of the RE Programme
Team	10			6	16	Direct Job benefit
Creative Bridge	7 ⁴	7	122	3	220 ⁵	Jobs and MVPs fully capture the impacts of Creative Programme

⁴ None of the creative bridge projects are recorded under jobs: it is assumed, therefore, that at minimum one job per start up may be attributed to “new jobs under this activity.”

⁵ Unlike all other training (which is defined as a CPD the Creative Bridge training maps to SCQF Level 11 (10 credit).

Programme	Jobs (Safe Guarded or New)	Spin outs, start-ups and pivots	MVPs	Products, Services, Experiences	Training	Assumptions
Creative Horizon				3		Not included: assumed not to be material/no job impacts recorded
Labs				6		Not included: assumed not to be material/no job impacts recorded
Studios				4	339	Training impacts unlikely to be material
Sub Total	332 ⁶	29	172	189	682	
(Inactive) ⁷	(40)	(5)	(6)	(25) ⁸	N/A ⁹	
Total	292	24	166	164	682	
Additional Outcomes	117	18	15	24	10	
Inactive deflator	88%	83%	97%	87%	N/A	
Net Effect	103	15	14	21	10	
Grand Total	405 ¹⁰	39	180	185	692	

⁶ Excluding 10 CI staff.

⁷ As per Supported Business by Strand DDI Report Excel Spreadsheet.

⁸ It is assumed that all 25 organisations who subsequently became inactive received this type of support.

⁹ Given the short term but also portability of CPDs it is assumed that benefits from participation can be captured in all cases.

¹⁰ Including the 10 CI staff.

APPENDIX A: CREATIVE INFORMATICS: INITIAL IMPACT ANALYSIS

INTRODUCTION

Outlined below are: estimates of the potential current and future gross economic impacts of the Creative Informatics (CI) programme; the key assumptions and supporting evidence (in Annex A) upon which these assumptions are based; and, observations on the limitations of the current projections and how these might be addressed going forward.

CURRENT AND FUTURE IMPACTS

Based on current CI estimates of job levels generated or safeguarded by the programme over 2019/20 to 2022/23, and accounting for subsequent programme participants business inactivity rates, Table One indicates a total (gross) level of £26.7 million Gross Value Added to the Scottish economy may be associated with the CI Programme.

TABLE ONE: ESTIMATES OF DIRECT CURRENT CI GROSS GVA LEVELS 2019/20 TO 2022/23

	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23	Total
Total New or Safeguarded Jobs (including 10 CI Team Members)	71.5	152.5	252	302	
"Average" GVA per head	33,300	33,300	33,300	33,300	
Total	£2.4m	£5.1m	£8.4m	£10.1m	£26m

As indicated, in Table Two below, if the 2022/23 participant job levels were to be maintained (i.e. assuming an even balance between some participant's organisations experiencing job growth while others may become inactive) then over the next three years a further £27.2 million GVA (in current price terms) might be generated.

TABLE TWO: POTENTIAL FUTURE GROSS IMPACTS IN CURRENT PRICE TERMS 2023/4 TO 2026/26

	2023/4	2024/5	2025/6	
Total Jobs ¹¹	292	292	292	
“Average” net present value ¹² GVA per head	£32,200	£30,800	£30,000	
Total	£9.4m	£9.0m	£8.8m	£27.2m

Combining the two estimates above suggests a total of £53.2 million GVA might be associated with the programme by 2025/26.

KEY ASSUMPTIONS

The analysis above is based on a series of assumptions, namely:

- The majority of impacts can be captured from the estimates of the total 292 jobs safeguarded or created (by 2022/3) as a result of participation in four of the CI programme activities (i.e. as illustrated in Table A1 Annex A: Challenge, Connected, Residential Entrepreneurs and Creative Bridge);
- Excluded from the current analysis, again as illustrated by Table A1, are any impacts associated with the 122 Minimum Viable Product (MVP) Activities under Creative Bridge; 3 Creative Horizon and 6 Lab projects and the 339 training participants under Studios. While these elements may generate further impacts they have currently been excluded because:
 - No evidence was provided of MVP outcomes (which over time if successfully commercialised could have significant relative impacts);
 - No jobs either safeguarded or created were recorded under the Creative Horizon or Lab projects; and,
 - Given the nature of training provided (i.e. in most cases CPDs) the 339 participants under Studios are unlikely to have a material impact.¹³
- Estimates of the GVA per employee are drawn from Scottish Annual Business Statistics data sets. Given the diverse nature of CI participants an average value has been adopted across three sectors, namely: the average GVA per employee in the Scottish Arts Entertainment and Recreation sector (over 2018 to 2020); Scottish Creative Industries (excluding the public sector) over 2019 to 2021; and, Sustainable Tourism Sector over 2019 to 2021.

¹¹ Excluding CI Team members.

¹² “The Green Book recommends that costs and benefits occurring in the first 30 years of a programme, project or policy be discounted at an annual rate of 3.5%”. <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/green-book-supplementary-guidance-discounting>

¹³ i.e. under the economic cases for all DDI hubs the benefit ascribed to CPDs was 3.6 x the individual cost of a paid for course. Assuming, therefore, that the opportunity cost of a CI CPD was £500 the 339 participants could be ascribed an annual only uplift of £170,000.

LIMITATIONS

As noted above MVP impacts may not be fully captured – particularly going forward – and they may also be potentially material in impact terms. Consequently it may be appropriate to conduct a survey of participants to elicit responses with regard to leveraged investment, revenue and employment effects associated with their MVPs.

It is also important to stress that the estimates above are in “gross terms” i.e. they do not account for any non-additionality. From a public sector perspective this is an important consideration: *“most interventions will have both positive and negative impacts. In appraising the effects of an intervention it is important that all of these are taken into account in order to assess its additional impact or additionality – in other words, the net changes that are brought about over and above what would take place anyway.”*¹⁴

In practice this requires judgements to be made concerning what CI participants may have done in the absence of the Programme¹⁵. Two common approaches to supporting such judgements are: comparing the outcomes of participants with either a similar peer group or a similar intervention and then comparing differences in outcomes to assess if there are any “additional impacts” that might be “attributable” to the CI programme. The other approach is to ask a sample of participants what alternative approaches they might have considered and what differences in outcomes they might have anticipated.¹⁶

In addition for “safeguarded” jobs the current estimates implicitly assume that the “counterfactual” position is that these individuals would otherwise be unemployed: the further the timescales adopted to project this effect the less likely this is the case. Consequently it may be necessary, if the CI data capture allows, to project “safeguarded job estimates” for a limited period only (of say one year).

Finally no multiplier values are applied to impacts. Firstly because no estimates have been made of non-additionality and therefore application of a multiplier will necessarily over-estimate total impacts. Secondly many public sector funders do not currently require such analysis and others tend to disregard multipliers in relation to funding decisions¹⁷.

¹⁴

https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/378177/additionality_guide_2014_full.pdf

¹⁵ As well as considering any displacement effects: i.e. whether CI uptake may have had any negative effects upon other providers. If it has this will “displace” or reduce any of the positive effects attributable to CI.

¹⁶ For example in a recent evaluation of the NI InnovateUs programme participants were asked two questions in this regard: (a) *“In the absence of the Programme what would you have put in place to support/improve staff skills development and innovation practices?”* and (b) *“Would this have led to different outcomes than occurred under the Programme and why (e.g. time, costs, skills, innovation focus etc.)?”*

¹⁷ If, however, additionality estimates were considered it is suggested adoption of the Scottish GVA Type II SIC code 72 (R&D) 2014 multiplier value of 1.5 for income based GVA benefits.

APPENDIX A

Table A1 outlines CI activities (i.e. in the first column under “programmes”), the KPIs recorded for each of these activities (i.e. jobs, MVPs etc.) the assumptions drawn for each programme in estimating gross impacts and the consequent coverage of the analysis (in green shaded cells) as well as the “gaps” (in the yellow shaded cells) that are implied by these assumptions

TABLE A1: CI ACTIVITIES AND KPIS

Programme	Jobs (Safe Guarded or New)	Spin outs, start-ups and pivots	MVPs	Products, Services, Experiences	Training	Assumptions
Challenge	52	5	12	31		Job impacts fully capture benefits of the Challenge Programme
Connected Innovator	57		4	50	27	Job impacts fully capture benefits of the Connected Programme
Resident Entrepreneurs	216	17	34	86	74	Job impacts fully capture benefits of the RE Programme
Team	10			6	16	Direct Job benefit
Creative Bridge	7 ¹⁸	7	122	3	226 ¹⁹	Jobs and MVPs fully capture the impacts of Creative Programme

¹⁸ None of the creative bridge projects are recorded under jobs: it is assumed, therefore, that at minimum one job per start up may be attributed to “new jobs under this activity.”

¹⁹ Unlike all other training (which is defined as a CPD the Creative Bridge training maps to SCQF Level 11 (10 credit)).

Programme	Jobs (Safe Guarded or New)	Spin outs, start-ups and pivots	MVPs	Products, Services, Experiences	Training	Assumptions
Creative Horizon				3		Not included: assumed not to be material/no job impacts recorded
Labs				6		Not included: assumed not to be material/no job impacts recorded
Studios				4	339	Training impacts unlikely to be material
Sub Total	342	29	172	189	682	
(Inactive) ²⁰	(40)	(5)	(6)	(25) ²¹	N/A ²²	
Total	302	24	166	164	682	

Table A2 details the calculations undertaken to profile the likely annual job lifts attributable to the four programmes which have captured job estimates.

²⁰ As per Supported Business by Strand DDI Report Excel Spreadsheet.

²¹ It is assumed that all 25 organisations who subsequently became inactive received this type of support.

²² Given the short term but also portability of CPDs it is assumed that benefits from participation can be captured in all cases.

TABLE A2 TIME PROFILE OF JOB EFFECTS EXCLUDING UOE CI TEAM BASED ON START-UP DATES²³

Activity	2019/20	2020/21	2021/22	2022/23
Challenge				
%	3%	27%	27%	43%
Total Jobs	52	52	52	52
Assumed spread	1.5	14	14	22.5
Aggregate	1.5	15.5	19.5	52
Connected				
%	N/A	33%	37%	30%
Total Jobs	N/A	57	57	57
Assumed spread	N/A	19	24	15
Aggregate	N/A	19	41	57
Creative				
%	27%	39%	22%	12%
Total Jobs	7	7	7	7
Assumed spread	2	3	1.5	0.5
Aggregate	2	5	6.5	7
Residential Entrepreneur				
%	27%	21%	42%	11%
Total Jobs	216	216	216	216
Assumed spread	58	45	92	21
Aggregate	58	103	195	216
Totals				
Overall Totals	61.5	142.5	262	332
Assumed Inactive effects			20	40
Final total	61.5	142.5	242	292

Table A3 provides the values and sources adopted to estimate the average GVA per head associated with the above job estimates (and the 10 CI team employees).

²³ Sourced from Supported Business by Strand DDI Report Excel Spreadsheet.

TABLE A3: GVA

Value	Source
£26,380 average GVA per head in Scottish Arts Entertainment and Recreation over 2018 to 2020	https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-annual-business-statistics-2020/documents/
£56,771 average GVA per head in Scottish Creative Industries over 2019 to 2021 (excluding the public sector)	https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-annual-business-statistics-2021/documents/
£16,607 average GVA per head in Sustainable Tourism Sector over 2019 to 2021	https://www.gov.scot/publications/scottish-annual-business-statistics-2021/documents/
Average: £33,253	